

Influence of dielectric constants on protonation equilibria of 5-sulfosalicylic acid and 5-hydroxysalicylic acid in urea-water mixtures

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Abstract : The solute-solvent interactions of 5-sulfosalicylic acid and 5-hydroxysalicylic acid have been studied in 0.0–42.47% w/v urea-water media using the pH-metric method. The protonation constants have been calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75. Selection of the best fit chemical model of the acid-base equilibria is based on standard deviation in protonation constants and residual analysis using crystallographic *R*-factor and sum of squares of residuals in all mass balance equations. Linear variation of protonation constants with inverse of dielectric constant of the solvent mixture has been attributed to the dominance of the electrostatic forces. Distributions of species, protonation equilibria and effect of influential parameters on the protonation constant have also been presented.

Keywords : Acid-base equilibria, 5-sulfosalicylic acid, 5-hydroxysalicylic acid, urea, protonation constant, dielectric constant.

Introduction

5-Sulfosalicylic acid (5-SSA) is used in urine tests to determine urine protein content. The chemical causes the precipitation of dissolved proteins, which is measured from the degree of turbidity. It has incompatibility with other materials such as, strong oxidizing agents and strong bases¹. 5-Hydroxysalicylic acid (5-HSA) is also known as Gentic acid which is a derivative of benzoic acid and a minor (1%) product of the metabolic break down of aspirin, excreted by the kidneys².

Urea acts as a denaturant of macromolecules but this action is reversible. The denaturant effect of urea on proteins can occur in two ways.

(1) Direct interaction of urea molecules with amide and peptide groups to destroy intermolecular hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions³ that are involved in the maintenance of ternary structures.

(2) Urea molecules exert their influence through changes

in water structures⁴. The increased solubility of some hydrocarbons in presence of urea supports the former mechanism⁵.

The present study deals with the dissociation and solvation processes in solutions of drugs and is important to elucidate the connection between chemical ability and biological activity. Salicylates are used as food preservatives. In addition, salicylic acid and its derivatives have been widely used in medicine (aspirin) and analytical chemistry. The dielectric constant of urea-water mixture decreases with increase in the mole fraction of urea. Hence this medium is chosen to study the acid-base equilibria to mimic the physiological conditions where the concept of equivalent solution dielectric constant for active site cavities of protein is applicable. In the present investigation we studied the protonation constants of 5-SSA and 5-HSA in urea-water mixtures and can be determined by analysis of acid-base titrations. Speciation profoundly influences both the

toxicity and bioavailability of an element. The data obtained would be useful to those working in biomedicine.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Solutions (0.05 mol L⁻¹) of 5-SSA (TCI, India) and 5-HSA (TCI, India) were prepared in triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ concentration of hydrochloric acid to increase the solubility. Urea (Qualigens, India) was used without further purification. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) pellets were used for the preparation of 0.4 mol L⁻¹ solution. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) solution of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. Sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) solution of 2.0 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain 0.16 mol L⁻¹ ionic strength in the titrand. Triple distilled water was used throughout the experiment. The strengths of acid and alkali were determined by using Gran plot method^{6,7}. To assess the errors that might have crept in to the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA)⁸.

Alkalimetric titrations :

All pH measurements were carried out at 303.0±0.1 K using pH meter (Equiptronics EQ 614 A). The sensitivity of pH meter is 0.01 units. The instrument could read pH in the range 0.00 to 14.00 by the stepwise addition of 0.1 ml of base. The pH meter was calibrated before each titration with an aqueous standard buffer solutions prepared from a 'Qualigens' potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 mol L⁻¹) and 'Qualigens' borax (0.01 mol L⁻¹) of pH 9.18 and 4.02 respectively at 303.0±0.1 K. In order to obtain steady and reproducible results in aquo-organic media the electrodes were pre-equilibrated with the respective media. So, the glass electrode containing inert electrolyte was equilibrated in a well stirred urea-water mixture for several days. The equilibration of the electrode should be done for each and every percentage of urea-water mixtures before the titration in that percentage. During the equilibration process, at regular intervals strong acid was titrated against alkali to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. The electrode

equilibration was continued if the residuals between the pH meters dial readings and the calculated pH values were not constant. The process has to be known as free acid base titration.

Alkalimetric titrations were carried out with varying composition of urea-water (0.0–42.47% w/v) mixtures by maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium chloride solution at 303.0±0.1 K. The amounts of 5-SSA and 5-HSA in the titrands ranged between 0.25 and 0.50 mmols. The details of the experimental procedure and titration assembly have been detailed elsewhere^{9–13}. In each titration, the titrand contained approximately 1 mmol of hydrochloric acid. The initial concentrations of ingredients are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) in proton-ligand titrations

Urea% (w/v)	TL0	
	5-SSA	5-HSA
0.0	0.2499	0.2449
	0.3748	0.3673
	0.4998	0.4898
5.8	0.2493	0.2493
	0.3740	0.3740
	0.4987	0.4987
11.52	0.2445	0.2488
	0.3667	0.3732
	0.4890	0.4977
20.31	0.2442	0.2510
	0.3663	0.3765
	0.4885	0.5021
29.63	0.2505	0.2483
	0.3757	0.3724
	0.5010	0.4966
36.83	0.2494	0.2437
	0.3667	0.3656
	0.4989	0.4875
42.47	0.2439	0.2499
	0.3659	0.3748
	0.4879	0.4998

Modeling strategy :

The approximate protonation constants of 5-SSA and 5-HAS were calculated with the computer program

SCPHD¹⁴⁻¹⁸. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD75¹⁹⁻²².

Results and discussion

Secondary formation functions :

Normal biochemical processes occur in aqueous solutions at about neutral pH. Physiological pH is about 7.2 to 7.4. Drugs present in biomolecules can gain or lose protons depending on the availability of hydrogen ions in the solution. This situation results in the simultaneous existence of a number of protonation-deprotonation equilibria in solution. Secondary formation functions like average number of protons bound per mole of ligand \bar{n}_H and number of moles of alkali consumed per mole of ligand (**a**) are useful to detect the number of dimeric species and equilibria. Secondary formation function (\bar{n}_H), average number of protons bound per mole of ligand and the equilibrium constants are related by an equation shown in eq. (1).

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{\beta_{011} \times FH + 2 \times \beta_{012} \times FH^2}{1 + \beta_{011} \times FH + 2 \times \beta_{012} \times FH^2} \quad (1)$$

where, $\beta_{011} = K_1^H$ and $\beta_{012} = K_1^H \times K_2^H$ and FH is the free hydrogen ion concentration. The computer program, SCPHD employs the below equation (eq. (2)) for the calculation of paired data (\bar{n}_H , pH).

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{(NDP + TLE + E + OH - ALK - FH)/TLE}{1} \quad (2)$$

Here NDP, TLE, E and OH are the number of dissociable protons of the ligand, total ligand concentration, total acid concentration and concentration of hydroxide ion due to auto ionization of water, respectively.

Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH (formation curves) for different concentrations of the ligand should overlap if there is no formation of dimeric species. Overlapping formation curves for 5-SSA and 5-HSA (Fig. 1) rule out the dimerization of the ligand molecules. All the titration curves were simulated by using computer programme MINQUAD75.

The pH values at half integral values of \bar{n}_H correspond to the protonation constants of the ligands. Two half integrals (0.5 and 1.5) in the case of both the ligands (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH in 29.64% w/v urea-water mixture : (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA; (\square) 0.25, (\circ) 0.38 and (Δ) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

emphasize the presence of two protonation-deprotonation equilibria in the pH range of present study.

The plots of **a** versus pH for 5-SSA and 5-HSA were given in Fig. 2. The negative values of **a** corresponds to the number of moles of free acid present in the titrand and the number of associable protons. The positive values of **a** indicate the number of dissociable protons in the ligand molecules. The maximum value of **a** in Fig. 2 is +3, which indicates that both 5-SSA and 5-HSA have three dissociable protons^{23,24}.

The best fit models containing the type of species and

Fig. 2. Variation of α with pH in 29.64% w/v urea-water mixture : (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA.

log values of overall formation constants ($\log \beta$) along with some of the important statistical parameters of the present study are given in Table 2. A very low standard deviation (SD) in $\log \beta$ values and U_{corr} (sum of the squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the model. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion.

Residual analysis²⁵ :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on the model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should be ideally equal to zero. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis of the least squares analysis, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , skewness, kurtosis, and R -factor. These statistical parameters of the present data show that the best fit models portray the acid-base equilibria of 5-SSA and 5-HSA in urea-water mixtures, as discussed below.

χ^2 test :

χ^2 is a special case of gamma distribution, whose probability density function is an asymmetrical function. This distribution measures the probability of residuals forming a part of standard normal distribution with zero mean and unit standard deviation. If χ^2 calculated is less than the table value, the model is accepted.

Crystallographic R -test :

Hamilton's R -factor ratio test²⁶ is applied in complex equilibria to decide whether inclusion of more species in the model is necessary or not. In pH-metric method, the readability of pH meter is taken as the R_{limit} , which represents the upper boundary of R beyond which the model bears no significance. When different values are obtained for models containing different number of species, models whose values are greater than R -table are rejected. The low crystallographic R -values given in Table 2 indicate the sufficiency of the model.

Skewness :

It is a dimensionless quantity indicating the shape of the error distribution profile. A value of zero for skewness indicates that the underlying distribution is symmetrical. If the skewness is greater than zero, the peak of the error distribution curve is to the left of the mean and the peak is to the right of the mean if skewness is less than zero. The values of skewness recorded in Table 2 are

Table 2. Best-fit chemical models of acid-base equilibria of 5-SSA and 5-HSA in urea-water mixtures

% w/v Urea	$\log \beta_1(\text{SD})$	$\log \beta_2(\text{SD})$	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R-Factor
5-SSA (pH range 1.70–11.30)								
0.00	10.92(1)	13.23(2)	91	7.65	0.12	3.03	6.66	0.0166
5.80	10.93(3)	13.28(5)	84	29.75	0.17	3.02	5.14	0.0360
11.52	10.97(4)	13.60(7)	90	50.56	0.10	2.72	15.38	0.0467
20.31	10.69(4)	13.90(9)	67	56.61	0.24	3.01	4.39	0.0619
29.64	10.72(3)	13.89(6)	59	30	0.26	2.69	0.78	0.0474
36.83	11.14(4)	14.49(7)	52	49.4	-0.11	2.25	25.08	0.0612
42.47	11.02(5)	14.43(7)	48	27.17	0.24	2.93	11.67	0.0433
5-HSA (pH range 1.70–11.30)								
0.00	10.23(1)	13.05(2)	145	6.53	-0.56	2.90	6.88	0.0110
5.80	9.88(2)	12.97(3)	92	19.22	0.69	3.40	3.65	0.0266
11.52	9.75(3)	12.64(6)	69	31.64	0.33	3.63	11.33	0.0403
20.31	9.79(4)	13.11(8)	55	44.90	0.13	3.39	3.45	0.0547
29.64	9.62(3)	12.78(7)	62	35.16	0.08	3.35	8.65	0.0457
36.83	9.69(3)	12.82(8)	18	8.43	0.42	3.00	1.33	0.0261
42.47	9.75(2)	12.93(7)	19	20.76	0.03	3.79	4.95	0.0316

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(\text{NP} - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of protonation constants; SD = Standard deviation

between -0.56 and 0.69. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data.

Kurtosis :

It is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a model value. For an ideal normal distribution kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic). If the calculated kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern in the case of 5-HSA and close to mesokurtic in the case of 5-SSA. The overlap of the typical experimental and simulated titrations data given in the Fig. 3 indicates that the proposed models represent the experimental data.

Alkalimetric titration data are simulated using the model parameters given in Table 2. These data are compared with the experimental alkalimetric titration data, to verify the sufficiency of the models. The overlap of the typical experimental and simulated titration data indicates that the proposed models represent the experimental data.

Effect of systematic errors in concentrations on best fit model :

MINIQUAD75 does not have an inbuilt provision to study the effect of systematic errors in the concentration of ingredients like mineral acid, alkali and ligand. In order to rely upon the best fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application, a brief investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the ingredients. This type of investigation is useful because the data acquisition was done under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies. The results of a typical system given in Table 3 emphasize that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acid affect the protonation constants more than that of the ligand.

Effect of dielectric constant of medium :

The dielectric constant is one of the characteristics of liquid. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants are strongly affected by the dielectric constant of the medium because of the fact that at least one of the constituents is charged and other is either charged or has a dipole. Variations in the relative strengths of acids and bases with changing solvents should be a function of the

Fig. 3. Simulated (solid lines) and experimental (o) alkali metric titration curves in 11.52% w/v urea-water mixtures : (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA; (a) 0.25, (b) 0.375 and (c) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

charge, the radius of the ion and the dielectric constants of the medium²⁷.

When the ionization of an acid gives a net increase of ions, a decrease in the dielectric constant of the solvent should be accompanied by an increase in the protonation constant of a weak acid dissolved in it. The variation of protonation constant or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change²⁸. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction or the loga-

Table 3. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the protonation constants in 5.8% w/v urea-water mixture

Ingredient	%	log β_{mlh} (SD)			
		5-SSA		5-HSA	
		LH ₂	LH ₃	LH	LH ₂
Alkali	0	10.93(3)	13.28(5)	9.88(2)	12.97(3)
	+5	10.32(3)	12.19(5)	9.42(3)	12.15(4)
	+2	10.70(3)	12.85(4)	9.70(2)	12.63(4)
	-5	11.70(8)	14.69(9)	10.36(5)	13.95(9)
Acid	-2	11.17(6)	13.74(7)	10.07(3)	13.23(6)
	+5	11.30(6)	14.12(8)	10.21(5)	13.76(10)
	+2	11.07(5)	13.59(6)	10.01(3)	13.27(6)
	-5	10.59(6)	12.53(8)	9.56(2)	12.27(3)
Ligand	-2	10.79(3)	12.98(4)	9.75(2)	12.69(3)
	+5	11.16(5)	13.69(7)	10.02(2)	13.15(4)
	+2	11.01(4)	13.42(8)	9.93(2)	13.03(4)
	-5	10.69(3)	12.85(4)	9.74(2)	12.79(4)
log F	-2	10.84(3)	13.13(5)	9.83(2)	12.91(4)
	+5	10.87(4)	13.08(5)	9.84(2)	12.85(4)
	+2	10.91(4)	13.21(5)	9.87(2)	12.93(4)
	-5	10.98(3)	13.44(5)	9.92(3)	13.08(5)
Volume	-2	10.95(4)	13.35(5)	9.90(2)	13.02(5)
	+5	10.93(4)	13.25(5)	9.88(2)	12.69(4)
	+2	10.93(3)	13.27(5)	9.88(2)	12.97(4)
	-5	10.92(4)	13.30(5)	9.88(2)	12.98(4)
	-2	10.93(3)	13.28(5)	9.88(2)	12.98(4)

rithm of stepwise protonation constant (log K) should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant ($1/D$) of the medium. Such linear variation of protonation constants (Fig. 4) of 5-SSA and 5-HSA in urea-water mixtures shows the dominance of electrostatic interactions. These drugs can exist in anionic and cationic forms in different equilibria investigated. The cation stabilizing nature of co-solvents, specific solvent-water interactions, charge dispersion, and specific interactions of co-solvent with solute, account for the deviation of classical linear relationship of log K with $1/D$. K_1 and K_2 are stepwise protonation constants for the reactions mentioned in Fig. 4.

Distribution diagrams :

Typical distribution plots produced by DISPLOT²⁹⁻³³ using protonation constants from the best fit models are shown in Fig. 5. A single representative plot is shown for

Fig. 4. Variation of stepwise protonation constants ($\log K$) with reciprocal of dielectric constants in urea-water mixture : (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA; (■) $\log K_1$ and (◆) $\log K_2$.

each system at a particular urea-water concentration. As the alkali is added to the titrand containing the ligands, the protonated forms of the ligands lose their protons. In the pH range 1.5–11.5, 5-SSA and 5-HSA lose carboxylic and hydroxyl protons successively.

5-HSA has three dissociable protons amongst them one protonation constant value is at pH more than 12.0 and 5-SSA has three protons, amongst them one protonation constant value is at less than pH 2.0. Due to the glass

Fig. 5. Species distribution diagrams of (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA in 20.31% w/v urea-water mixture.

electrode sensitivity in between pH 2.0–12.0, we are unable to study the pH more than 12.0 and less than 2.0. The distribution plot of 5-SSA (Fig. 5(A)) shows the existence of LH_2^- , LH^{2-} and L^{3-} at pH ranges 1.5–7.0, 1.5–11.0 and 7.0–11.0 respectively. The LH^{2-} is present to an extent of 96% in the pH range 1.5–11.0.

The distribution plot of 5-HSA (Fig. 5(B)) shows the existence of LH_3 , LH_2^- and LH^{2-} at pH ranges 1.5–6.5, 1.5–11.5 and 5.5–11.5 respectively. LH^{2-} is present to an extent of 98% in the pH range 1.5–11.5. The corresponding protonation-deprotonation equilibria are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of (A) 5-SSA and (B) 5-HSA.

Conclusions

- (1) 5-SSA has three dissociable protons and exists as LH_3 . The existence of LH_3 form cannot be observed, as the deprotonation takes place at pH less than 2.0. While increasing the pH, LH_3 deprotonates and exists in the form of LH_2^- , LH_2^{2-} and L^{3-} .
- (2) 5-HSA has three dissociable protons and exists in the form of LH_3 at low pH. While increasing the pH, it deprotonates into LH_2^- , LH_2^{2-} and L^{3-} . The existence of L^{3-} form cannot be observed, as the deprotonation takes place at pH more than 12.0.
- (3) The change in the magnitude of protonation constants with co-solvent content indicates the influence of dielectric constant of the medium.
- (4) Secondary formation functions, number of moles of alkali per mole of the ligand and average number of moles of protons bound per mole of the ligand are useful in detecting the number of protonation-deprotonation equilibria and in guessing the approximate protonation constants.
- (5) The linear variation of log values of protonation constants of both 5-SSA and 5-HSA with increasing dielectric constant of urea-water mixtures indicate the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria.
- (6) The effect of systematic errors in the influential parameters shows that the errors in the concentrations

of alkali and mineral acids will affect the protonation constants more than that of the ligand, log F and volume.

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